

Square Printed Monopole Antenna for Wireless Applications

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Abstract : In this article design and optimization of square printed monopole antenna for wireless application is proposed. Theory of characteristics mode (TCM) is used for analyses of current modes on the antenna. TCM analysis shows beveled ground plane improves the impedance bandwidth. Antenna operates from 1.860 GHz to 5 GHz for a VSWR ≤ 2 , covers GSM (1900-1990MHz), IMT-2000(1920-2170MHz), Bluetooth (2.400-2484 MHz), lower band of ultrawideband. Stable radiation pattern shows minimal pulse distortion. Size of proposed antenna is 39 mm x 29 mm x 1.6mm. Antenna is simulated using CAD FEKO suite (6.2) using method of moment. FR4 dielectric substrate with a dielectric constant of 4.4 and loss tangent of 0.02 is used for fabrication of antenna. Simulated and measured results of the proposed antenna are presented and agrees quite well.

Keywords : DGS, Theory of characteristics mode, UWB, VSWR.

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